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SIGNIFICANCE OF UROMODULIN IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND PROGRESSION OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE.

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ANNOTATION

Uromodulin (Tamm-Horsfall protein) is produced in the kidney by cells of the thick ascending limb and distal tubule. Recent genetic studies suggest a role of uromodulin in chronic kidney disease. Mutations in the UMOD gene cause uromodulin storage disease. They code for amino acid substitutions that lead to misfolding of the molecule and its retention in the endoplasmic reticulum. Single nucleotide polymorphisms in the region of the UMOD gene have been shown to be associated with chronic kidney disease and reduced glomerular filtration rate. These polymorphisms affect uromodulin concentration in the urine, and lower genetically determined urinary uromodulin concentrations seem to protect against renal disease. Chronic kidney disease is associated with higher serum levels of uromodulin. From animal experiments and human studies it is hypothesized that uromodulin entering the renal interstitium either by basolateral secretion or urinary back-leakage in damaged tubuli interacts with and stimulates cells of the immune system and thereby causes inflammation and progression of chronic kidney disease.

Keywords: Uromodulin, Tamm-Horsfall protein, Chronic kidney disease, genetic, urinary

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ЗНАЧЕНИЕ УРОМОДУЛИНА В РАЗВИТИИ И ПРОГРЕССИРОВАНИИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ ПОЧЕК

АННОТАЦИЯ

Уромодулин (белок Тамма-Хорсфалла) продуцируется в почках клетками толстой восходящей ветви и дистального отдела канальца. Недавние генетические исследования предполагают роль уромодулина при хроническом заболевании почек. Мутации в гене UMOD вызывают болезнь накопления уромодулина. Они кодируют аминокислотные замены, которые приводят к неправильной укладке молекулы и ее удержанию в эндоплазматическом ретикулуме. Было

показано, что однонуклеотидные полиморфизмы в области гена UMOD связаны с хроническим заболеванием почек и снижением скорости клубочковой фильтрации. Эти полиморфизмы влияют на концентрацию уромодулина в моче, а более низкие генетически обусловленные концентрации уромодулина в моче, по-видимому, защищают от почечной недостаточности. Хроническая болезнь почек связана с более высоким уровнем уромодулина в сыворотке крови. Эксперименты на животных и исследования на людях позволяют предположить, что уромодулин, попадая в интерстиций почек либо путем базолатеральной секреции, либо путем обратного подтекания мочи в поврежденные канальцы, взаимодействует с клетками иммунной системы и стимулирует их, тем самым вызывая воспаление и прогрессирование хронического заболевания почек.

Ключевые слова: уромодулин, белок Тамма-Хорсфалла, хроническая болезнь почек, генетика, мочевыводящие пути.

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SURUNKALI BUYRAK KASALLIKLARI RIVOJLANISHI VA PROGRESSIYALASHISHIDA UROMODULINING AHAMIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Uromodulin (Tamm-Horsfall oqsili) buyrakda qalin ko'tarilgan va distal kanallari tomonidan ishlab chiqariladi. So'nggi genetik tadqiqotlar surunkali buyrak kasalligida uromodulinning rolini ko'rsatadi. UMOD genidagi mutatsiyalar uromodulinni saqlash kasalligini keltirib chiqaradi. Ular molekulaning noto'g'ri qatlamlanishiga va uning endoplazmatik retikulumda saqlanishiga olib keladigan aminokislotalarni almashtirishni kodlaydi. UMOD genidagi yagona nukleotid polimorfizmlari surunkali buyrak kasalligi va glomerulyar filtratsiya tezligining pasayishi bilan bog'liqligi ko'rsatilgan. Ushbu polimorfizmlar siydikdagi uromodulin kontsentratsiyasiga ta'sir qiladi va genetik jihatdan aniqlangan siydikdagi uromodulin kontsentratsiyasining pastligi buyrak kasalliklaridan himoya qiladi. Surunkali buyrak kasalligi qon zardobida uromodulinning yuqori darajasi bilan bog'liq. Hayvonlarda o'tkazilgan tajribalar va odamlarda o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, uromodulin buyraklar oraliqlariga bazolateral sekretiya yoki shikastlangan kanalchalardagi siydik orqa oqishi bilan kiradi va immunitet tizimining hujayralari bilan o'zaro ta'sir qiladi va ularni rag'batlantiradi va shu bilan surunkali buyrak kasalligining yallig'lanishi va rivojlanishiga sabab bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Uromodulin, Tamm-Horsfall oqsili, Surunkali buyrak kasalligi, genetik, siydik

Uromodulin was first discovered by I. Tamm and F.L. Horsfall in 1950, when they isolated a protein from urine that inhibited hemagglutination of viruses [1, 2]. At first, after the name of the authors, the protein was called the Tamm-Horsfall protein (THB). In 1985 A.V. Muchmore and J.M. Decker isolated a protein from the urine of pregnant women, which was named uromodulin (UMR), because it showed immunosuppressive effects on T cells in vitro [3]. Soon D. Pennica et al. demonstrated that the amino acid sequences of UMO and TCB are almost identical [4]. Since that time, ULV and TCB have been used interchangeably for the same protein. To date, a lot of convincing evidence has been accumulated that TCB is a multifunctional protein. It is critical for modulating renal ion channel activity, fluid balance, renal and systemic inflammatory responses, intertubular interactions, urinary mineral crystallization, and bacterial adhesion. In addition, mutations in the ULV gene cause a group of congenital kidney diseases, and changes in TCB expression are associated with an increased risk of urinary tract infections, stone formation, hypertension, hyperuricemia, and acute injury or chronic kidney disease [5]. Nevertheless, many

issues, primarily related to the involvement of the UMO in physiological and pathological processes, remain extremely controversial (“uromodulin paradoxes”) [6].

Structure, synthesis and secretion of uromodulin.

UMO is a glycoprotein with a molecular weight of 80–90 kDa [3, 4, 7, 8] expressed in the epithelial cells of the thick ascending loop of Henle (TLHOH) [9, 10] and, possibly, the initial parts of the distal tubule [6,7,11]. This protein is encoded by the UMOD gene. TCB consists of several domains and is largely glycosylated (30% of molecular weight) [7, 8]. UMO is a glycosylphosphatidylinositol (GPI)-anchored protein with an interesting structure and unique properties [7]. The precursor protein consists of 640 amino acids [4]. Regions identified in the primary sequence of TCB include a signal sequence directing it to the secretory pathway (residues 1–24), one epidermal growth factor-like domain (EGF-like domain) (residues 31–64), two calcium-binding EGF-like domains (residues 65–107 and 108–149), a D8C domain containing eight cysteine domains (residues 199–287), a fourth EGF-like domain (residues 295–319) [12], one zona pellucida (ZP) domain (residues 334–585), eight potential N-glycosylated domains, and a GPI-binding domain (residue 614). 48 cysteine residues are involved in the formation of 24 disulfide bridges. It is assumed that EGF-like domains mediate the interactions of the THP protein, while the ZP domain promotes self-aggregation and polymerization [13]. In TLHOPG, the ULV focuses mainly on the apical pole, which is additionally facilitated by the presence of the GPI anchor, which plays the role of the “target apical signal” [14, 15]. When UMO is secreted into urine, proteases cleave its GPI anchor from the protein [16]. During biosynthesis, the UMO precursor is translocated to the endoplasmic reticulum (ER), where the signal peptide is removed and the protein is glycosylated at seven of its eight potential glycosylation sites [17]. Disulfide bonds are formed, and a preformed GPI anchor is attached to the C-terminus (most likely S614) [15]. After that, TCB is transported to the Golgi apparatus, where, after a series of transformations, complex glycans are attached to the molecule. Both mature glycans and the GPI anchor target the protein predominantly to the apical membrane of epithelial TrHOPG cells [18,19]. It is assumed that the UMO reaches the luminal side of the plasma membrane in a conformation unsuitable for polymerization, which is preserved as a result of the interaction of two hydrophobic motifs.

One of them is located within the ZP domain and is called the internal hydrophobic patch (IHP, residues 430–462); the other is located between the ZP domain and the GPI anchor site (outer hydrophobic spot, EHP, residues 598–607) [12, 20]. Proteolytic cleavage by the recently identified hepsin protease disrupts the hydrophobic interaction between IHP and EHP and generates a polymerizable monomer, which subsequently assembles into polymer filaments [21, 22]. Ultimately, TCB is secreted into the urine in the form of a high molecular weight polymer ($M_r \frac{1}{4} 1-10106$ Da), which, under electron microscopy, looks like a fibrillar matrix capable of assuming a gel-like structure depending on ionic strength [23]. The urinary monomer ULV consists of 563 amino acids. Monomeric forms of this glycoprotein in urine have been reported after the addition of urea [24]. It is also possible to isolate a truncated form of TCB from urine, in which part of the ZP polymerization domain is missing [13]. This form is predominantly monomeric, although it can also form dimers since it retains the N-terminal portion of the ZP domain [25]. It is believed that the rate of TCB maturation is limited by processing in the ER. This is due to the complex tertiary structure of the protein due to the presence of a large number of cysteine residues (48.7% of the amino acid content), which are involved in the formation of intramolecular disulfide bridges [7]. In the ER, as noted above, glycosylation is initiated at seven of the eight potential N-linked glycosylation sites. In the Golgi complex, all glycan chains are converted into complex cleaved carbohydrates with sialic acid residues at the ends, with the exception of N274, which retains a fragment with a high mannose content [17]. O-linked glycosylation is also possible [26]. Thus, glycosylation makes a significant contribution to the molecular weight of THP (as already mentioned above, about 30%). This high carbohydrate content is believed to be important for the physicochemical properties and functions of TCB [13]. Independent studies have shown the presence of a smaller but significant basolateral ULV secretion, i.e. protein release into the blood [9, 27]. For example, when using immunoelectron microscopy of rat kidneys, S. Bachmann et al. showed that the ratio of apical/basal ULV secretion is 2:1 [9]. It is

known that ULV is determined in the blood serum of healthy people at concentrations of 30–540 ng/mL [28–30]. The significance and mechanisms of basolateral ULV traffic have not been fully elucidated. However, it has been established that the circulating forms of TCB are predominantly monomeric [13]. It also remains unclear why ULV does not aggregate in the systemic circulation, despite the total length of the molecules [6, 11]. Finally, little is known about changes in the synthesis and the ratio of apical and basolateral variants of ULV transport in acute and chronic injuries of the tubulointerstitial compartment of the kidneys. Some researchers believe that basolateral ULV transport may even predominate (or, in any case, suffer less) over apical transport in the development of kidney damage [31]. Hence, there is a reasonable desire to use the ratio of basal and apical TCB secretion as an estimated indicator characterizing the state of the tubulointerstitial compartment of the renal parenchyma. However, there is no single point of view regarding the predominance or, conversely, a decrease in one or another type of secretion as damage to the tubulointerstitium develops [31]. In the available literature, we found only one work performed at the modern level, in which the value of apical (into the urine) and basal (into the blood) ULV secretion was estimated depending on the severity of morphological changes established during nephrobiopsy [32]. According to the results of a number of studies, the daily excretion of ULV in the urine in healthy people ranges from 9 to 66 mg [29, 30, 34–36], although some authors also cited higher values: 70–113 mg [28, 37].

It can be assumed that a certain contribution to the variability of this parameter is made by differences in the mass of active nephrons among study participants, the use of different methods for measuring ULV in urine, and a small number of observations in each individual study. ULV excretion increases from birth to adulthood and remains stable until about 60 years of age, after which it begins to decrease [38, 39]. At the same time, the ratio of urine uromodulin/urine creatinine remains relatively constant from the age of four until the seventh decade of life. ULV excretion positively correlates with eGFR, urine volume, salt and protein intake [30, 36, 40]. The half-life of ULV in the blood is about 16 h in humans [41]. UMO is present in urine mainly as a high molecular weight polymer (M_r 1–10×10⁶ Da) in the form of fibrils. In electron microscopic analysis, the fibrils have a width of about 100 Å and an average length of about 25,000 Å. UMO is a polyanionic macromolecule intensely sialylated and sulfated by N-linked glycans [42]. In solutions, UMO, aggregating, exhibits gel-like properties at NaCl and CaCl₂ concentrations close to 100 and 1 mmol/L, respectively [19, 18], which can serve as an explanation for the physiological fact of the appearance of single hyaline cylinders in the urine sediment during dehydration (for example, in athletes), which causes an increase in the concentration of electrolytes in the urine. The secreted ULV forms a slow moving gel that interacts with molecules of the same protein anchored to the plasma membrane. This could potentially contribute to the colloid osmotic pressure of urine and slow down the passage of cations in the thick ascending loop of Henle, thus facilitating their reabsorption and transport in this segment of the nephron [11, 43], which ultimately affects the activity countercurrent multiplier system of the kidneys.

Potential clinical significance of uromodulin.

Findings from genome-wide association studies Interest in ULVs has increased as a result of genome-wide association studies (GWASs). Such studies have shown the existence of relationships between a common single nucleotide polymorphism in the ascending (upstream) region of the UMOD gene with the state of renal excretory function and arterial hypertension [53]. The results of molecular genetic studies have made a new and significant contribution to understanding the mechanisms of TCB involvement in the mechanisms of regulation of the functioning of the renal tubules, sodium homeostasis and blood pressure. The latter can potentially serve as a basis for creating new approaches to the treatment of arterial hypertension [44]. Using PPAS in healthy people, it was found that the alleles of the UMOD gene associated with low levels of UMO in urine (rs12917707, rs4293393, rs13333226) correlate with higher GFR values [33–51]. Associations of single nucleotide polymorphisms of the UMOD gene with GFR suggest that they are the cause of variations in the glomerular filtration rate in healthy people [51]. Based on the results of the studies cited above [53], one would expect that at the lowest concentrations of ULV in urine, GFR should take the highest

values. One of the available explanations for this is associated with the information that the corrected daily urinary excretion of TCB (expressed in $\mu\text{mcg/ml}$ of creatinine clearance) increases in patients with CKD [36] and in patients with diabetes mellitus in the early stages of diabetic nephropathy without a clear decrease in GFR as in both cases [24]. These data can be interpreted as follows. The reduction in the total mass of active nephrons in the initial stages of chronic damage to the renal parenchyma is accompanied by compensatory hyperfiltration in the remaining nephrons (therefore, GFR remains at a normal level) and hyperfunction of the cells of the ascending thick loop of Henle (therefore, the number of UMOs in a single functioning nephron increases) [22].

Therefore, in patients in the early stages of CKD with preserved GFR, an increase in the total urinary excretion of TCB can be expected [44]. However, a more pronounced decrease in GFR, reflecting a decrease in the mass of functioning nephrons due to their irreversible damage, may be accompanied by a concordant decrease in the concentration of TCB in the urine (decrease in the synthesis of TCB due to a decrease in the mass of functioning tubules) [30, 36]. Another explanation is based on the results obtained by L.A. Graham et al. Their studies, among other things, compared changes in creatinine clearance in intact and knockout (UMOD^{-/-}) mice after salt loading. It was found that creatinine clearance significantly decreases in knockout animals under basal conditions, but significantly increases after salt loading [50]. This suggests that in the early stages of CKD with preserved GFR and, contrary to expectations, low rather than high urinary ULV concentrations, high salt intake may be the cause [29]. In general, data on the causal role of ULV in the modulation of kidney function, based on the data of various available studies, are contradictory, and the search for mechanisms pathogenetically linking genomic changes identified as a result of PPAS with GFR has not yet been completed [25].

Significance of TCB in the development and progression of CKD.

The results of many studies, including those performed in recent years, indicate that urinary excretion of ULV decreases as the functional state of the kidneys deteriorates [32]. At the same time, J. Zhou et al. [18] found no relationship between urinary TCB levels and basal eGFR in a study of 344 patients with IgA nephropathy. In this regard, it should be borne in mind that their study included patients with relatively intact kidney function (mean $\pm$ error in mean eGFR: 83.7 ± 1.6 ml/min/1.73 m²). The latter necessarily, in our opinion, could prevent the identification of such an association. In turn, A. Köttgen et al. received data that rather indicate an increase in the concentration of ULV in the urine with a decrease in GFR [17]. However, their results were derived from the Framingham Heart Study (FHS) and Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities (ARIC) population studies. At the same time, lower levels of GFR and higher values of ULV concentration in urine were observed in homozygotes for the C-allele of carriers of polymorphism rs4293393 of the UMOD gene. Recently, separate studies have appeared that have studied the association between renal excretion of TCB and morphological manifestations of damage to the structure of the kidneys in patients with some variants of glomerulopathies. When examining patients with IgA nephropathy, it was found that the concentration of ULV in the urine is lower in cases of severe manifestations of tubular atrophy and interstitial fibrosis [18,19]. In patients with CKD, the maximum degree of tubular atrophy was noted with a simultaneous decrease in ULV levels in blood serum and urine [32]. There are suggestions that TCB can directly participate both in the development of kidney damage and provide nephroprotection [6, 10]. Both of these conclusions are drawn from the highly contradictory and sometimes even paradoxical results of clinical and experimental studies. Some data suggest a pro-inflammatory role for UMO, which has a specific ability to activate neutrophils, monocytes, and dendritic cells [36]. ULV urine of pregnant women enhances the phagocytic activity of neutrophils with the participation of prostaglandin E₂. This does not exclude the direct specific interaction of TCB with neutrophil membranes [35]. UMOD^{-/-} mice show splenomegaly associated with marked infiltration of the white pulp by macrophages and increased concentrations of TNF- α and interleukin-1. The ability of TCB to activate bone marrow dendritic cells is realized through its interaction with Toll-like type 4 receptors (TLR4). ULV acts as a trigger orienting dendrocytes towards the formation of a mature maternal phenotype [46]. It matters in inflammation and modulation of a congenital immune response. The identification of endocytosis formations containing the complex of the GFI

with the UMOs assigned to the idea of the presence of an immunosuppressor TCB, which are implemented by binding to the tumor- α necrosis factor (TNF- α) and the interlay Macrophages of bone marrow origin can also be activated by urodulin. Intravenous administration of UMO is accompanied by the products of cytokines of macrophage origin. At the same time, the results of some clinical and experimental observations show that TCB deposits in renal tissue do not have decisive values in the inflammatory process. In particular, R. Chambers et al. In kidney biopsy, did not find the correlation between the accumulation of UMOs in the interstition and the severity of inflammatory changes in the tubules [40]. In addition, the absence or low-intensive inflammatory response to this glycoprotein was revealed in renal grafts with the presence of interstitial pathology [41]. Although the results of In vitro experiments suggest that the formation of antibodies to the UMO can be crucial for fixing the inflammatory response [42], such antibodies are not necessary to form a response to this protein in vivo [43]. Returning to the issue of basolateral traffic TCB, we note that so far remains unclear whether the UMO appears in the renal interstices due to the return of urine back or by secretion through the basolateral tubular. Studies in ischemic damage have shown that UMO drifts from the apical to the basolateral domain of the canalic cell, which can confirm the basolateral origin of an interstitial UMO. This is associated with activation by the signaling mechanism of signaling paths of inflammation in the nearby proximal tubules [31]. T.m. El-Achkar and X.R. Wu, trying to somehow associate contradictory and ambiguous information about the role of UMO in damage to the kidneys (in particular in the regulation of the immune response), concluded that the TCB could show a pro-inflammatory effect on a militant. At the same time, according to the first scenario, the effect of UMO is preferably aimed at stimulating dendritic cells, which should clean the kidney tissue from cell detritus formed when induced renal damage. The activation of TCB in this case by the negative feedback mechanism suppresses the signaling paths of inflammation in the cells of the epithelium. According to the second scenario, UMO urine and glycoprotein coming in interstices due to basolateral secretion, have different immunogenic properties. Such differences are determined by the peculiarities of the glycosylation of these two types of protein. The OMO, which occurred due to basolateral secretion, interacts with certain receptors on the membranes of tubular cells, which leads to the oppression of the signaling paths of inflammation in them [6]. In this context, it is significantly that recently there have been information that parts of the TCB molecule can be used (at least in the future) for anti-TNF- α -therapy in inflammatory diseases, antibodies. Despite the elegance of T.M. scientific schemes. El-Achkar and X.R. Wu, it seems to us that they are far from fully consistent with many available data. Important question: Can TCB itself modulate kidney damage due to the same inflammatory response? The answer to it is ambiguous. For example, S. Bachmann et al. Did not find morphological features of the renal tissue (including at the ultrastructural level) in mice knocking on the UMO gene, compared with wild-type animals. The interaction of TCB with cells and the effectors of the immune system is characterized by complex and ambiguous mechanisms. For example, it has long been known that UMO has the ability to bind inflammatory cytokines and Complete C1Q [5-7].

In this case, the activation of the alternative path of the Complement is involved in the development of tubulone-interstitial damage [8], and the Complement Factor H - CFH) is decisive in the regulation of this process [8]. It can bind to the surface of the escalation tubular cells and inhibit the activation of the complement with ischemic damage to the kidneys [9]. Chinese specialists were able to show that UMO, binding to CFH, activates it. CFH, in turn, interacting with C3B, speeds up the degradation of the latter. All this, ultimately, suppresses the activation of the complement on an alternative path, which is associated with a smaller expression of damage to the renal tissue in patients with different nephropathies [9]. The results of another already quoted clinical study showed that the low level of EMO excretion is connected not only with greater severity of tubul interstitial damage, but also a large risk of accelerated reduction of RSKF in patients with IGA nephrop. This data seemed to indicate the nephroprotective effect of TCB. However, in population studies, it was found that the increased concentration of UMOs in the urine associated with the most common UMOD polymorphism precedes the start of the development of the HCB [5]. Finally, patients with nephropathies found positive dependencies between the concentrations of TCB in serum and a number of pro-inflammatory cytokines [32]. Thus, the available information does not give

unambiguous evidence in the benefit of the damaging, nor in favor of the nephroprotective role of the TCB in nephropathies, and this issue requires additional research. The role of uromodulin in the regulation of sodium homeostasis and the development of arterial hypertension. There are consistent and distinct evidence of the participation of UMO in the regulation of sodium homeostasis and blood pressure [52]. RS13333226 G-alleles Umod-gene (associated with low TCB) are characterized by a low fractional sodium excretion in the conditions of free consumption of a salt and low fractional excretion. The associations of the RS13333226 genotype and the excretion of UMO with urine become more distinct at low sodium consumption, but weaken with a high content of this cation in the diet [53]. Such data suggest that the Hypertension associations with RS13333226 are mediated by the UMO and, possibly, its influence on sodium homeostasis. M. Trudu et al. and L.A. Graham et al. Performed experiments complementing each other, providing further evidence of the important role of TCB in the regulation of sodium balance and the development of arterial hypertension [14]. L.a. Graham et al. It has shown that Umod - / - mice are characterized by significantly lower levels of systolic blood pressure compared to wild-type animals [30]. Nocturnal mice turned out to be resistant to salt-induced changes in blood pressure, and they have observed a shift in the pressure of the pressure-noderase [30]. M. Trudu et al., On the contrary, found that the super-symbol of the Umod-gene (study on transgenic mice) causes dose-dependent activation and an increase in the excretion of the UMO associated with the growth of hell They were also able to show that Furosemide significantly increases sodium and reduces blood pressure from both transgenic mice and hypertensive individuals, homozygous alleles associated with a high level of TCB [Finally, in recent work it was shown that the young, knockout on Umod, mice there are renal losses of salt and water, but with age in such animals, expressed oliguria develops, which is associated with the activation of the compensatory reabsor Such a reaction seems to be partially mediated by the activation of the renin followed by the development of arterial hypertension [33]. These studies confirm that the relationship between UMO and hypertension is mediated through sodium transport in the thick ascending department of the loop of Genla.

In turn, the influence of UMO on sodium reabsorption in TLVOG is realized through the necrosis factor of the tumor-alpha (TNF- α) and sodium / potassium / 2 chlorine-boot carrier (NKCC2) [34 In a simplified form, the TCB place in the regulation of sodium transport to TLVOP, mediated via NKCC2, is presented in the figure. At the same time, the UMO, who secreted into the lumen of the Channel, binds TNF- α there, which, in turn, cannot interact with its receptor (TNFR) and show the inherent inhibiting effect on NKCC2. Ultimately it turns out that under the influence of TCB NKCC2 becomes more active, and the transport of ions in the TLVOP increases. The results of the majority of experimental work discussed above are mainly consistent with the assumption that UMO is capable of activating sodium tubular reabsorption and, thus, reduce its renal excretion. However, the data obtained in clinical and population studies, for the most part indicate that the excretion of UMO with urine positively correlates with the removal of sodium [39, 47,]. The reasons for such contradictions remain not quite clear, but they emphasize the need to further study this problem. Recently, the fact that TCB has an effect on tubular reabsorption and other ions, in particular, bivalent. It should be noted that changes in the activity of NKCC2 themselves are affected by the transport of cations, primarily CA and MG in TLVPG (due to the impact on the value of the lumenopositive transverse potential difference). Therefore, it can be expected that the variations of the concentration of UMOs in tubular fluid can affect the excretion of these cations. However, the correlation between the daily excretion of TCB, the volume and osmolality of urine, the removal of Na, K and Ca or the clearance of free water in healthy people was not observed [36]. On the other hand, information was obtained that with overpressing TCB (activating mutation), sodium reabsorption increases and, possibly, the tubular transport K, CL, CA and MG [10] changes. It is possible that changes in calcium and magnesium transport are also associated with the activating effect of UMO on TRPV5 (the increase in the reabsorption of Ca) and TRPV6 (the increase in reabsorption Mg) [13-15] Despite the fact that dysfunction of the homeostasis of bivalent cations may have an important pathogenetic significance in the HCB and participate in the development of its complications (including arterial hypertension), clinical studies on the participation of TCB in this By the poet, we consider the search

for associations between the products / excretion of the UMO and the homeostasis or the excretion of bivalent cations in patients with the HBA in an interesting and relevant issue. The excretion of uromodulin with urine in the diagnosis of gravity of the HBS and the differential diagnosis of various options for glomerulopathies there are separate messages in which the associations were studied mainly between the characteristics of the renal excretion. When examining patients with IGA nephropathy [6,9] or other kidney diseases [32], it was found that the concentration of UMOs in the urine below in cases of expressed manifestations of tubular atrophy and interstitial fib. This made it possible to propose the use of the value of the excretion of TCB as an indicator of the tubular function [12-16]. The clear specificity of the Place of Biosynthesis UMO suggests that the excretion of this glycoprotein with urine can characterize not only the tubulointerstitial kidney compartment, but also their state as a whole, including the level of mass of existing. This has a number of indirect confirmations [17]. It is interesting, however, that with this task (the integral characteristics of the kidney state), in our opinion, is better not to cope not by urinary excretion of TCB, but the concentration of this protein in the blood serum (see below).

Currently accumulated information also make it possible to believe that the assessment of the parameters of apical (renal excretion parameters) and the basolateral (serum concentration) of the UMO transport may be significance not only for the forecast of the progression of the HCB, On the other hand, the identification of certain associations between the peculiarities of clinical and morphological manifestations of nephropathies with a number of metabolic and transport indicators of TCB prompted to test the possibilities of using such data for differential diagnostics. Such directions are currently starting to be developed. One of the main tasks of these approaches is to develop technologies that allow, in particular to identify the form of glomerulopathy, without resorting to nephrobiopsia. They are most often based on the results of the proteoma urine analysis and (or) serum. Thus, in the study of urine proteomics, it was shown that non-priodasitive forms of glomerulopathy [the disease of minimum changes (BMI) and membrane nephropathy (MN)] are associated with higher levels of alpha fragments. In turn, in the focal-segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS), the content in the urine of the same fragment of the UMO (M / Z 1945) was as high as during proliferative versions of glomerular. In the next work of the same group of Catalan authors, the ideas of differential diagnosis of BMI and FSGS were developed. In this case, the content in the urine of one of the fragments of UMO in patients with FSGS was significantly higher than in patients with BMI. While the urinary levels of the derivatives of alpha1-antitriplein, as a whole, were higher at BMI than with FSGS. On the basis of the data obtained, these researchers have developed a computer program that allows a rather high degree of confidence to distinguish such options for glomerulopathies [19]. It was also confirmed to separate IGA-nephropathy from other glomerulopathy variants based on the content of Fragment M / Z 1913.14 [20]. The results of the studies cited above are based on the use of urine proteoma analysis methods. Such methods usually make it possible to identify certain fragments of the corresponding protein molecules (in particular TCB), but these methods are difficult to reach clinical practice. Therefore, it is of interest and further assessment of the differential-diagnostic significance of changes in the total concentration of TCB in the urine, especially in the complex with changes in the excretion of other proteins and the level of TCB in serum. The diagnostic value of the concentration of uromodulin in serum should be borne in mind that most studies in which they tried to estimate the relationship of the UMO with the features of the functional state of the check, clinical manifestations of nephropathies or morphological changes in the soaring. However, in recent years, serious interest in the values of the concentration of this protein in serum (plasma) of the blood, including in terms of diagnostics, began to be serious. At the same time, as already mentioned, the amount of serum concentration of UMO closely correlates closely with the RSKF level in patients with HBP [33], and its changes make it possible to detect the presence of chronic kidney damage than some other panel markers. In addition, it has recently been shown that patients with low levels of serum UMO have significantly greater chance of the development of HBS than people with a high concentration of this glycoprotein [25]. It is important to emphasize that in the studies cited above, very large patient cohorts have been studied. For example, L. Risch et al. 279 participants examined, and D. Steubl et al. - 426 [21, 22]. All this can serve as an indirect confirmation

of the above assumption that the concentration of TCB in blood serum to a certain extent is a fairly clear reflection of the renal state as a whole. In this regard, it remains only to regret that in most works that evaluate the diagnostic importance of serum UMOs, urinary levels of this protein were not commonly studied.

The AK has already been noted above, in the affordable literature we found only one work, in which they tried to directly analyze the links between the concentration of uroductulin in serum, the characteristics of its urinary excretion and morphological changes in the renal fabric in pain. In this work, in patients with HBA, the maximum degree of tubular atrophy is noted while reducing the levels of UMO in serum and urine [32]. However, unlike L. Risch et al., D. Steubl et al. and other S. Prajczek et al. Did not find a distinct association between the RSKF and the concentration of UMO in the blood serum [12, 21, 22]. Moreover, their data, rather, give reason to believe that the relationship between these parameters is inverse ($RS = -0.1821$; $p = 0.1083$). The results of the already quoted work with our participation [33] indicate that in patients with glomerulopathies, the concentration of uromodulin in serum, apparently, is more closely associated with RSKF, the severity of the Glom. However, as an integral assessment of the state of the kidneys, the serum concentration of TCB does not exceed the SCF, but it may make it possible to detect damage to the tubula interstitial kidney compartment, than the speed of glomerular filtration [33]. Based on the above information, it is necessary to recognize that the relationships (especially in the complex) of product characteristics / excretion of the UMO with the features of the functional state of the kidneys, clinical manifestations of nephropathy or morphological changes in renal 1.8. Uromodulin and autosomal dominant tubulin-interclassical kidney disease completed this review, pay attention to another aspect of the possible participation of TCB in the development of renal pathology. We are talking about some genetically deterministic kidney diseases. As is known, the HBE is a polyetiological state, and far from all the reasons that cause chronic damage to the kidneys are well known. The volume of knowledge of hereditary and congenital kidney diseases is continuously increased [26]. According to the data available to date, the monogenic disorders are still the cause of the HBA in less than 10% of cases. On the other hand, in a dialysis population of patients, it is often traced to the difficulty "family". This suggests that the true frequency of genetically deterministic kidney diseases is underestimated [26-28]. The results of perennial observations, confirmed by the data of the last molecular genetic studies, showed that the mutations of the UMO gene (not to be confused with Umod genetic polymorphisms!) Could cause the HBD and call: family. All new cases continue to be described and analyzed groups of patients with nephropathies associated with UMOD mutations, to clarify the features of clinical manifestations and genetic defects underlying these diseases. A detailed study of this issue made it possible to conclude that all the states mentioned above are different phenotypes of the same genetically deterministic disease inherited by autosomal dominant. Such phenotypes combines the presence: hyperuricemia (possibly with manifestations of damage to the joints of the gout type), low fractional excretion of uric acid (less than 5%) and, on the contrary, is the absence: hypertension. A number of studies have demonstrated that mutations not only uomod, but also genes encoding the synthesis of some other proteins (mucin, renin, etc.) can lead to a similar clinical picture. However, the main unifying signs for such states remain an autosomal dominant inheritance and the development of tubulointerstitial damage to the kidneys. All this in 2015 made it possible to come to a consensus in relation to the presence of new genetically deterministic renal pathology - autosomalized tubulin-interclassical kidney disease (ADTBE) (Table) [43]. At the same time, the general clinical manifestations in patients with ADTBP are becoming already mentioned autosomal dominant inheritance, progressive renal function, poor blades, lack of or insignificant albums.

According to our experience, patients (including female), with hyperuricemia, manifestations of gouty arthritis arising in a relatively young age, a decrease in the function of the kidneys, the lack of pronounced proteinuria and / or changes M. They represent a difficult diagnostic problem, since it is difficult to reduce their diagnosis only to the early development of gout and gout nephropathy. Taking into account the above information, it is impossible to exclude that at least the part of them may have an adtbp-umod. In any case, the study in such patients with concentrations and the parameters of renal excretion of TCB may be undoubted interest.

CONCLUSION

Currently information on the importance of changes in metabolism and excretion of OMO in patients with CBDs of the incomplete nephropathy (including glomerulopathy) indicate that the excretion (and possible products) of this g There are a number of certificates about the potential participation of TCB in the progression of nephropathies, modulation of renal transport of ions and the development of arterial hypertension during HBS. A certain perspective may have the possible diagnostic value of biosynthesis and removal characteristics. However, specific data on all these issues is often insufficient or contradictory ("paradoxes of uroduodulin") [6]. All these questions require further study.

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